

Prevalence of Postpartum Depression and its associated factors among postnatal mothers in Trichy.

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Postpartum depression usually occurs two to eight weeks after giving birth but can happen up to a year after the baby is born. "One of the important things about postpartum depression is it's not just feeling sad. Postpartum Depression has been recognized as important public health problem as it impacts both the health of the mother and development of the child. Global Prevalence of postpartum depression as 17.22 %. Developed and Higher Income Countries have lower prevalence of postpartum depression. Various factors contribute to depression in postnatal period which includes unwanted pregnancy, marital status, gender of the baby, inadequate social support, family support, coincidental life support.

Objectives: To assess the prevalence of Postpartum Depression & to find out its associated factors among postnatal women in rural field practice area of a tertiary care centre, Trichy.

Methodology: A community based cross sectional study was conducted in rural area of Trichy. A total of 250 study participants were selected by simple random sampling. Postpartum Depression was assessed using EDPS Scale.

Results: A total of 250 postnatal mothers were included in this study. Prevalence of Postpartum Depression among postnatal mothers was found to be 22%. The factors that were statistically significant includes mode of delivery, gender related issues, family support, emotional support & breast feeding

Keywords: *Postnatal mothers, Postpartum Depression, Prevalence, Edinburgh postnatal depression scale score, Associated factors, Mental Health.*

INTRODUCTION

Awareness about postpartum depression arose during late 1980s. Throughout the pregnancy women experiences a roller coaster ride of psychological, physical, emotional and hormonal changes. And her delivery will be a tough & exhausting process. It will change her familial and interpersonal world. Varied emotions are experienced by her from happiness to crying bouts [1] Psychiatric disorders during the postnatal period can be classified into three categories: postpartum blues; postpartum psychosis and postpartum depression [2]

According to UNICEF, Postpartum depression usually occurs two to eight weeks after giving birth but can happen up to a year after the baby is born. "One of the important things about postpartum depression is it's not just feeling sad." [3] Women are more prone to postpartum psychiatric disorders which includes depression, anxiety & attachment disorders [4].

Postpartum Depression has been recognized as important public health problem as it impacts both the health of the mother and development of the child⁵. People fail to recognize postpartum depression even though it has serious consequences. It halts the relationship of the mother with growing infant which leads to malnutrition and other complications in the mother [6]. This subsequently leads to maternal mortality and morbidity raising it as a public health problem [7]

According to a study done by Wang et al & Liu et by mapping global prevalence of depression among postpartum women it stated that the Global Prevalence of postpartum depression as 17.22 %. Developed and Higher Income Countries have lower prevalence of postpartum depression [8]. According to a community based study done in rural south India prevalence of postpartum depression was found to be 11%[9]. Various factors contribute to depression in postnatal period which includes unwanted pregnancy, marital status, gender of the baby, inadequate social support, family support ,coincidental life support([10],[11]). The other factors which also includes previous history of depression & anxiety[12],negative attitude towards pregnancy, breast feeding, young age ,empathy relations, socio economic status, employment status ,education[13]. In this study we also include factors like adequate help during pregnancy, attitude towards handling baby. This study aims to assess the prevalence of postpartum depression and its associated factors among postnatal women in rural field practice area of tertiary care centre, Trichy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A questionnaire based cross sectional study was conducted in rural field practice area of Tertiary Care Centre at Trichy from June 2024 to November 2024 for the period of 6 months. Women from day 1 of delivery to 42 days after delivery residing in rural field practice area of a Tertiary Care Centre were included in this study. Postpartum mothers who were not willing to give consent were excluded. The sample size of 247 was calculated using the formula $(z^2_{1-\alpha}pq)/d$. The prevalence (p) of postpartum depression among postnatal women by Dadhwal et al & Sagar et al was 5.6% [14] with 3% absolute precision with 95% confidence level the adequate expecting about 5% dropout rate it is decided to take. The total sample size is 250. Ethical Committee approval was obtained before starting the study. Written informed consent in the native language (Tamil) was obtained from the study participants. Study Participants were selected using Simple Random Sampling technique. Data was collected using a predesigned prevalidated questionnaire consisting of 3 parts. Part 1 consists of Socio-demographic details, In the part 1 section preexisting illness includes history of chronic diseases like Diabetes, Hypertension, Tuberculosis & Asthma. History of psychiatric illness in their family includes all types of psychiatric diseases. Socioeconomic Status is classified using Modified BG Prasad's Scale 2024. part 2 consists of factors of postpartum depression, part 3 had Edinburg Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS) which had a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.81. There were ten questions in the scale each scoring from 0 to 3 with a maximum score of 30. A score of 12-13 is likely to be suffering from clinically relevant depression & need to seek medical attention [15]. The study participants were asked whether they had those symptoms during the postpartum period for 7 or more consecutive days. Data Entry was done in Microsoft excel.

Statistical analysis

The data were entered and analysed using SPSS version 26.0. The study variables were assessed for normal distribution. Descriptive measures such as mean and standard deviation were calculated for normally distributed data. Chi-square test will be used to compare proportion. For all statistical tests of significance, p value less than 0.05 will be considered as significant. The data will be entered and analysed using SPSS version 23.0.

RESULTS

A total of 250 postnatal mothers were included in this study. Table .1 indicates the socio demographic characteristics of study participants. Of which majority (43.2%) of postnatal mothers belongs to 19-25 years. According to total number of family numbers most (96%) of the postnatal mothers have 2-6 members in their family. Most of the post-natal mothers were studied up to elementary school (41.2%) and were financially dependent (72.4%). Preexisting illness and family history of postpartum depression were absent. Majority (36%) of them belongs to lower middle class.

Table 1: Socio Demographic Characteristics (n=250)

Characteristics	Category	Frequency (n%)
Age	19-25 years	108(43.2%)
	26-32 years	106 (42.4%)
	33-39 years	26(11.6%)
	40-46 years	7(2.8%)
Total Number of Members in the family	2-6	235(94%)
	7-12	15(6%)
Educational Status of the mother	Illiterate	2(.8%)
	Elementary School	103(41.2%)
	High School	33(13.2%)
	Under Graduate	64(25.6%)
	Post Graduate	6(2.4%)
Financial Status	Independent	69(27.6%)
	Dependent	181(72.4%)
Pre Existing Illness	Present	2(.8%)
	Absent	248(99.2%)
Family history of Psychiatric Illness	Present	5(2%)
	Absent	245 (98%)
Family History of Postpartum Depression	Present	14(5.6%)
	Absent	236(94.4%)
Socio-economic status	1(Upper Class)	38(15.2%)
	2(Upper Middle Class)	18(7.2%)
	3 (Middle Class)	75(30%)
	4(Lower Middle Class)	90(36%)
	5(Lower Class)	29(11.6%)

Figure 1 demonstrates the prevalence of Postpartum Depression:

Prevalence of postpartum depression among postnatal mothers was 22%. Out of 250 post-natal mothers 55 of them were found to have postpartum depression as seen in Figure.1.

Table II denotes the relationship between factors associated with postpartum depression and the prevalence of postpartum depression.

The statistically significant factors associated with postpartum depression were mode of delivery, plan on their pregnancy, pressure to deliver male child, wanted son but delivered daughter. complication during delivery, complaints of domestic violence, history of psychiatric complaints in 1st degree family members, spouses were taking Alcohol, adequate relationship with in laws, Support from husband, Adequate breast milk, Attitude in handling the baby, adequate help during postpartum which is shown in Table II.

Table II. :Factors Associated with Postpartum Depression

Factors Associated with PPD		PPD		p value
		Yes (n=55)	No (n=195)	
Mode of Delivery	Normal Vaginal Delivery	25(10%)	119(47.6%)	p=0.03*
	C-Section	30(12%)	76(30.4%)	
Total number of girlchildren do you have	1	22(8.8%)	80(32%)	p=0.5
	>1	24(9.6%)	72(28.8%)	
	Nil	9(3.6%)	43(17.2%)	
Present Pregnancy	Planned	36(14.4%)	161(64.4%)	p=0.21*
	Unplanned	13(5.2%)	25(10%)	
	Unwanted	6(2.4%)	9(3.6%)	
Pressure to have a male child	Yes	17(6.8%)	28(11.2%)	p=.005*
	No	38(15.2%)	167(66.8%)	
Wanted Son but delivered daughter	Yes	26(10.4%)	26(10.4%)	p=0.00*
	No	29(11.6%)	169(67.6%)	
Complication during pregnancy	Yes	23(9.2%)	70(28%)	p=0.4
	No	32(12.8%)	125(50%)	
Complication during delivery	Yes	26(10.4%)	30(12%)	p=0.00*
	No	29(11.6%)	165(66%)	
Complaints of domestic violence	Yes	13(5.2%)	4(1.6%)	p=0.00*
	No	42(16.8%)	191(76.4%)	
History of psychiatric complaints in 1st degree family members	Yes	12(4.8%)	16(6.4%)	p=0.005
	No	43(17.2%)	179(71.6%)	
Closely attached to the partner	Yes	40(16%)	161(64.4%)	p=0.10
	No	15(6%)	34(13.6%)	
Husband taking alcohol	Yes	24(9.6%)	51(20.4%)	p=0.01*
	No	31(12.4%)	144(57.6%)	
Adequate relationship with the parents	Yes	45(18%)	173(69.2%)	p=0.17
	No	10(4%)	22(8.8%)	
Adequate relationship with the in-laws	Yes	30(12%)	170(68%)	p=0.00*
	No	25(10%)	25(10%)	
Is your husband supportive & understanding	Yes	42(16.8%)	189(75.6%)	p=0.00*
	No	13(5.2%)	6(2.4%)	
Support from in-laws during pregnancy	Yes	31(12.4%)	168(67.2%)	p=0.00*
	No	24(9.6%)	27(10.8%)	
Do you breastfeed your child	Yes	48(19.2%)	175(70%)	p=0.6
	No	7(2.8%)	20(8%)	
Is your breastmilk adequate for your child	Yes	33(13.2%)	165(66%)	p=0.00*
	No	22(8.8%)	30(12%)	
.Do you have difficulty in breastfeeding	Yes	22(8.8%)	54(21.6%)	p=0.8
	No	33(13.2%)	141(56.4%)	
Were you felt afraid of handling the baby	Yes	27(10.8%)	55(22%)	p=0.04*
	No	28(11.2%)	140(56%)	
Did you have adequate help during your postpartum period	Yes	32(12.8%)	151(60.4%)	p=0.004*
	No	23(9.2%)	44(17.6%)	

*p value <0.05 will be taken as statistically significant

DISCUSSION

In this current study, Prevalence of postpartum depression is 22% among post-natal mothers assessed using Edinburgh's Postpartum Depression Scale. This was almost similar to the other studies done by Panolan et al & Thomas et al (22%) [16] And other study by Wedajo et al & Alemu et al (22.9%) [17] and another Indian Study by Lanjewar et al & Nimkar et al shows prevalence as 26% [18]. An Irish study done by Fiona et al which showed prevalence of 14.4%. [19] & An Ethiopian Study by Wubetu et al in Ethiopia showed prevalence of 15.6%. [20] which showed lesser prevalence than our study might be due to lesser sample size. Other study by Randhawa et al & Chaudary et al states the prevalence of postpartum depression as 32.8% [21] which is higher than our study, as it was a hospital-based study whereas our study is a community-based study.

There is significant association between age & postpartum depression in this study. Similar to the population-based study done by Silverman et al & Reichenberg et al [22]. Whereas age shows negative correlation according to the study done by Ou et al & Gao et al [23]. As they didn't strictly classify postpartum depression. The significant factors associated with postpartum depression in this study like the issue related to breast feeding is similar to the study conducted by Angarat et al & Berg et al [24]. Other significant associated risk factors like Age, mode of delivery, gender related issues of wanting male baby, domestic violence & family support in our study findings were similar to the community-based study conducted by Sundaram et al & Jogdand et al in [25].

The factors like gender related issues, maternal social support, domestic violence was found to be as significant associated factors by the study done by Wedaju et al & Alemu et al which is similar to this study [17]. Poor Quality interpersonal relationship found to be significant associated factor according to study by Hammen et al which is similar to this study [26]. Social Support has protective effect on postpartum depression stated by Reid & Oliver et al which is similar to this study [27].

CONCLUSION

Postpartum Depression is the most important neglected public health problem in Indian population affecting mother, new born & family. Early screening and timely treatment can reduce postpartum depression. Much importance towards health education during antenatal period to the pregnant mothers & their families might create awareness for postpartum depression. By concentrating on these modifiable risk factors, we can reduce the prevalence of postpartum depression. Preventing postpartum depression includes the coordinated support of pregnant mothers, families, field staffs, psychiatrists, gynaecologists, public health specialists, psychologists, medico social workers. More extensive longitudinal studies in the community will help us find out more risk factors.

Strengths:

As community Based Cross Sectional Studies on Post partum depression in India are limited this study will help us to identify the potential risk factors in postpartum depression. This study will help the policymakers to include mental health in reproductive & child health programs. Based on this training can be provided to ASHAs & ANMs in early screening for postpartum depression during their postnatal visits.

Limitations:

More factors can be included to narrow down the risk factors for postpartum depression. As it was observational cross sectional study cause effect relationship couldn't be studied.

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